

Social Media and Academic Performance: A Case Study of GJUST Students

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the relationship between social media use and academic performance among students at Guru Jambheshwar University of Science and Technology (GJUST) in Hisar, Haryana. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect data from 100 students, and 80 valid replies were analyzed, giving an 80% response rate. Based on the findings, most students had smartphones with internet access and were active on several social media sites. Daily usage ranged from 1 to 2 hours, with a large percentage spent on non-academic activities such as chatting and browsing. The findings showed a negative effect of social media use and academic performance. The researchers suggest encouraging students to use digital technologies for academic objectives, such as online research and e-learning platforms.

Introduction

Social media has become an integral part of everyday life, playing a significant role in communication, collaboration, and information sharing, including within educational institutions (Boyd & Ellison, 2007; Odnokaya et al., 2022). The rapid growth of social media usage, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, has created new opportunities for online student engagement, learning, and educators (Tkacová et al., 2022). These platforms facilitate the exchange of educational resources, support group discussions, and promote collaborative learning. According to Tkacová et al. (2022), trusted social media platforms can transform students from passive learners into active participants, contributing to a more dynamic and engaging learning environment.

At the same time, the worldwide adoption of platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, TikTok, and X (formerly Twitter) has led to a surge in social media use among youth globally (Adorjan & Ricciardelli, 2021; Neelakandan et al., 2020; Odgers & Jensen, 2020). The appeal of short, viral videos, memes, and humorous sketches makes these platforms highly engaging, especially for younger audiences. While this trend increases connectivity and creative expression, it also raises concerns about distractions and reduced academic focus.

A quality education, free from excessive digital distraction, is crucial in preparing young people to compete in a dynamic global economy. Without a solid academic foundation, students may face challenges adapting to the evolving demands of the modern workforce (Neelakandan et al., 2020). Social networking platform like Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Twitter have undeniably changed how students connect, collaborate, and learn. Growing up in a digital environment, students increasingly use these platforms for educational purposes, including resource sharing, group assignments, and communication (Junco, 2012). While these tools can enhance learning by providing peer support and access to information (Tess, 2013), they may also lead to reduced study time, poor concentration, and diminished academic performance if not used responsibly (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). With near-constant smartphone use, the boundaries between academic and personal life have blurred, contributing to issues related to time management and focus (Murtaza, 2024). Thus, while social media can support learning, its dual role as both a helpful resource and a potential distraction necessitates deeper academic investigation.

Researchers find this study significant as they examine how social media use affects the academic performance of students at GJUST, a topic they often overlook in regional contexts. While most existing studies have focused on global or urban settings, this study provides local insights that can help educators and policymakers understand students' media habits and develop strategies to support academic success.

Review literature:

This study uses the uses and gratifications and cognitive load theories to understand why students use social media, how much they access it, and its impact on their academic performance. These theories help to explain students' motivations and how excessive use may affect their learning and focus.

- 1. Use and gratification theory:** In 1973, Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch formulated this concept. This theory tells how people use social media to satisfy their desires. Everyone has a different reason to

use social media, some of use for entertainment, some of use education, some of use information, and others stay connected to friends.

For example, some students use Facebook for entertainment and to stay connected with friends, and some use YouTube as an academic resource; thus, we say that both are using social media for different reasons.

- 2. Cognitive Load Theory:** This theory was developed by John Sallwer (1988). This theory states that the human mind holds a limited amount of information simultaneously. If students spend a lot of time on social media, they are easily distracted. Their brains become overloaded; in this situation, it is difficult to focus on studying and learning new things. Example: If a student continues to check Facebook or Instagram and other social networking sites while studying, their attention is divided. This can make it harder for them to remember what they have studied and can affect their academic performance.

According to Junco et al. (2010), Social media comprises a conglomeration of online platforms, services, and practices that promote cooperation, community enhancement, engagement, and sharing. The increasing prevalence of social media among contemporary youth is undeniable. The use of social networking among students in the second cycle has become increasingly common throughout the period of time. It enables you to engage with friends both off-campus and on-campus. Social networking enables numerous individuals to perceive themselves as members of an expansive group. In light of its increasing popularity, economists and scholars are questioning whether students' academic performance is affected by the amount of time they dedicate to these sites (Choney, 2010). M. and Selvara (2013).

According to a well-structured questionnaire used in this study of 150 students from the Islamic University in Kushtia, Bangladesh, 73% of students primarily utilize social media platforms that are not for academic purposes. The majority of students use social media sites like Facebook for more than four hours per day, mostly in the evening and early morning. The data imply that excessive use of social media negatively affects academic achievement. The report suggests that parents, teachers, and university advisers actively educate and supervise kids to minimize social media overuse and encourage balanced use. Bison et al. (2018). According to this study, social media use negatively affects academic achievement. It also shows that science students benefit from reduced smartphone usage during study sessions. Female humanities (arts) students perform worse than their male counterparts. Latif et al. (2020).

According to this study, academic performance is negatively impacted by increasing social media use, especially among youth. Addiction is more common among teenagers, who often use social media for enjoyment for more than three years. Although not statistically significant, one finding ($p = 0.061$) strongly suggests that study time was negatively affected. A longer duration of use was significantly associated with purposeless social media engagement ($p = 0.000$). Overall, excessive social media use reduces study time, which adversely affects academic performance. Kumar et al. (2021). This study identified a slight negative association between academic performance and social media use among undergraduate medical students. Excessive usage, particularly among low-performing pupils, was linked to greater addiction rates. While many students utilized platforms like WhatsApp and YouTube for academic objectives such as assignments and research, generally, social media generally had a detrimental influence on academic achievements. Palla and Sheikh (2021). According to the paper, the majority of college students in Kashmir utilize social media, namely YouTube, for educational objectives such as coursework and skill development. When used properly, social media improves academic achievement by allowing students to access material, exchange expertise, and stay current in their professions. Goet, J. (2022). This study, based on a multi-stage sample of 360 college students, investigates the impact of several social media activities such as video watching, media sharing, internet browsing, and video gaming on academic achievement. Using correlational and causal study methodologies, the findings show that these social media elements have a considerable favourable impact on students' academic achievements. Based on the study, when utilized constructively, these platforms may improve students' attention and help them build their future careers. Ahmad et al. (2023).

According to this study, a survey of 200 college students in rural Pakistan, social media use has a big impact on academic achievement and has both advantages and disadvantages. While social media allows for networking and information sharing, which can improve academic performance, it also adds to bad behaviors like procrastination, daydreaming, and diminished study and family time. The findings underscore the multifaceted role that social media plays in students' academic and personal lives, underlining the importance of balancing its usage for educational benefits with its disruptive impacts. Zaw et al. (2023). The study of 267 medical students from the University of Cyberjaya discovered an important connection between social media use and academic achievement. Excessive usage was associated with worse grades and poor time management. The studies also highlighted gender variations in usage habits, underlining the importance of time management and being mindful of social media's detrimental academic impacts. Alam et al. (2023). This qualitative case study, based on the critical theory of technology, investigated students' perceptions of social media use and discovered that it had a

detrimental impact on academic achievement. Students reported spending too much time on non-academic activities, which resulted in poor time management, worse grades, and health concerns such as stress and physical tiredness. Jan et al. (2024). This research of university students in Punjab and Pakistan discovered that greater social media use is associated with higher cognitive load, which has a detrimental impact on academic performance. Strong self-regulation abilities, however, let pupils better control these impacts. The study also revealed that students who used social media less were far more motivated. These results point to the necessity of initiatives to encourage responsible usage and emphasize the significance of self-regulation in mitigating the negative academic effects of social media. Lukose and Agbeyangi (2025).

According to a study conducted at Walter Sisulu University's Buffalo City Campus, excessive social media use has a negative influence on academic achievement, particularly among first-year students. With 84.5% spending more than four hours per day on social media and 39.4% saying that it interferes with assignment completion, the study highlighted social media as a significant distraction. While technology can aid in learning, the study underlines the need for time management and academic use. Zhu et al. (2025). This study differentiates between academic and excessive social media usage, showing that academic motivation fosters productive use while avoiding excessive involvement. Academic social media use enhances students' perceptions of academic success but has little effect on actual outcomes. On the other hand, heavy usage seriously impairs real academic results yet does not influence perceived performance. These results highlight the necessity of promoting academic motivation and balancing social media use to reduce its detrimental impact on academic achievement.

There is limited research focusing on how social media use affects academic achievement among students at state universities, such as GJUST and Hisar. Most of the existing studies have focused on the global context. Often neglects localized student experiences and their direct impact on academic performance. This study addresses that gap by examining this relationship in a specific local context.

This study aimed to determine how students use social media and how much time they spend on it per day. Also, researchers want to know the relationship between social media use, time spent on social media per day, and students' academic performance

Objective:

1. To examine the impact of social media on students' academic achievement.

2. To identify the benefits of social media.
3. To identify how students use social media platforms.

Methodology:

In this research, the researcher used quantitative data analysis. The survey method was used to collect data from Guru Jambheshwar University of Science and Technology, Hisar, Haryana. A standardized questionnaire was created to collect data. A stratified sampling technique was used to sample respondents from the different departments. To improve the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, it was pretested. The results obtained were used to design a questionnaire to analyze the purpose of the study. A total of 100 samples were used in this study.

After data collection, the research was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The frequency and percentage results are shown in table, frequency, and percentage. The researchers distributed the questionnaires, but 80% were returned. Respondents were given between 20 and 30 minutes to complete the questionnaires. The questionnaire was sent via email and WhatsApp via Google Forms.

Hypothesis:

Null hypothesis: There is no relationship among time spent on social media and academic performance or achievements.

Findings:

Demographic profile of the respondent:

Serial Number	Variables	Description	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Age	20-25	58	72.5%
		26-30	13	16.3%
		31-35	07	8.7%
		35 above	02	2.5%

2.	Gender	Female	40	50%
		Male	40	50%
3.	Qualification	Graduation	35	43.8%
		Post-Graduation	25	31.3%
		Pursuing PhD	20	25.0%
4.	Area	Urban	45	56.3%
		Rural	35	43.7%

Source: Primary data

Table 1: Distribution of the students

Institute	Sample size	Number of respondents	Percentage %
GJUST	100	80	80%

Source: Primary data

Research takes 100 samples, and 80 students respond to the questionnaire.

Graph 2: Favorite social media platforms:

Source: Primary data

This table shows that Snapchat 28 represents 35.0%, WhatsApp 24 represents 30.0%, Instagram 16 represents 20.0%, Facebook 8 represents 10.0%, and X 4 represents 5.0%. This means that students' favorite social media platform is Snapchat.

Graph 3: Time spent on social media platforms:

Source: Primary data

This table shows Almost half of students spend 2 to 3 hours every day on social media platforms. The rest of them, 1 to 2 hours, 18, represent 22.5%, 3 to 4 hours, 16, represent 20.0%, 4 to 5 hours, 10 represent 12.5%.

Graph 4: Why students utilize social media:

Source: Primary data

The data clearly shows most of the students use social media platforms for communication and social media interactions (40%), then for entertainment (30%), then for academic and educational work (17.5%), and then for casual browsing (12.5%).

Graph 5: Social media affects students' academic performance:

Source: Primary data

The table shows that 71.25% of students said social media uses affect their study. Then 16.25% said no social media use does not affect our study, and 12.5% in doubtful.

Graph 6: Improved academic work through social media:

Source: Primary data

Only 20, which means 25.00% of students said yes to social media use improving academic performance, and most of the students, 53 (66.25%), said social media use does not improve academic performance, and 7 (8.75%) were not sure about this.

Correlations:

Variable	Time spent	Academic performance
Time spent	1	-0.65
Sig. (2-tailed)	–	0.001
N	80	80
Time spent	-0.65	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001	–
N	80	80

The relationship between the independent variable (social media time) and the dependent variable (academic performance) identified a significant negative relationship. The Pearson correlation value was -0.65, showing a significant negative relationship Correlation between the two variables. This implies that as the duration of time spent on social media increases, academic performance tends to decline. The association was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p = 0.001$), based on an 80-person sample. This finding confirms that excessive use of social media can adversely affect students' academic outcomes. In practical terms, students who spend more time on social media are likely to experience a decline in academic performance, suggesting the need for greater awareness and time management among students regarding their social media usage.

Conclusion

The study examined how social media affects student achievement. Most respondents had mobile internet access and were familiar with social media. Results further revealed that students typically spent between one to five hours daily on these platforms. It was self-evident from the study that students were

already aware that excessive use of social media could negatively affect their academic performance. This observation highlights a serious issue, as students continue to engage extensively with social media despite knowing its potential consequences on their academics. Therefore, it is crucial for students to develop self-awareness regarding the time spent on social media and to practice better control over its use to maintain a healthy academic balance.

The study also revealed that students' academic performance was negatively influenced by their social media consumption, supporting the notion that a significant relationship exists between social media usage and academic achievement (Dhiman, 2022). The hypotheses H1 and H2, which examined the time spent on social media platforms and their association with academic performance, indicated a strong positive correlation at the 0.01 significance level. Furthermore, the survey found that most students primarily use social media for communication purposes rather than for educational or learning-related activities. In other words, excessive engagement with social media tends to result in a decline in academic performance. Additionally, students reported experiencing related challenges such as anxiety, depression, and setbacks in career development.

Limitations of the study

This study was limited to GJUST Hisar and Haryana students. In this study, the researcher selected 100 students, but only 80 students responded. This research is based on social media use, and researchers want to understand the academic performance of students. This research does not apply to all fields and is not generalized.

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